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STRATEGY “DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN-2030”: INNOVATIVE-INTEGRATION DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURE ECOLOGICAL-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND AN IMPORTANT STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS OF EMPLOYMENT OF THE RURAL POPULATION

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СТРАТЕГИЯ “ЦИФРОВОЙ УЗБЕКИСТАН-2030”: ИННОВАЦИОННО- ИНТЕГРАЦИОННАЯ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА, ЭКОЛОГО- ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ И ВАЖНЫЕ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЗАНЯТОСТИ СЕЛЬСКОГО НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

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“RAQAMLI O‘ZBEKISTON-2030” STRATEGIYASI: QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION-INTEGRATSION RAQAMLASHTIRISH EKOLOGIK-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISH VA QISHLOQ AHOLISINI ISH BILAN TA‘MINLASHNING MUHIM STRATEGIK YO‘NALISHLARI

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abstract

Currently, there is a rapid growth in the use of the digital economy on a global scale in almost all branches of human activity. Agriculture is no exception, including in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in which in recent years a number of decrees and decrees of the President have been adopted in the field of digital economy development.

аннотация

В настоящее время наблюдается стремительный рост использования цифровой экономики в глобальном масштабе практически во всех отраслях человеческой деятельности. Сельское хозяйство не является исключением, в том числе и в Республике Узбекистан, в которой за последние годы был принят ряд указов и распоряжений Президента в области развития цифровой экономики.

annotatsiya

Hozirgi vaqtda inson faoliyatining deyarli barcha sohalarida raqamli iqtisodiyotdan global miqyosda foydalanishning jadal o'sishi kuzatilmoqda. Qishloq xo'jaligi bundan mustasno emas, shu jumladan so'nggi yillarda raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish sohasida O'zbekiston Respublikasida ham Prezidentning bir qator farmon va farmonlari qabul qilingan.

Keywords:

Progress of digitalization, agro-industrial complex, concept, “environmentally sound agriculture”

Ключевые слова:

Прогресс цифровизации, агропромышленный комплекс, концепция, “экологически безопасное сельское хозяйство”.

Kalit so'zlar:

raqamlashtirish taraqqiyoti, agrosanoat majmuasi, kontseptsiya, "ekologik toza qishloq xo'jaligi".

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Currently, there is a rapid growth in the use of the digital economy on a global scale in almost all branches of human activity. Agriculture is no exception, including in the Republic of Uzbekistan, where in recent years a number of presidential decrees and decrees have been adopted in the field of digital economy development. Agriculture has always been one of the priority areas. Now there are tasks for the digitalization of the industry.

An international conference organized by the Financial Institute of India was held on January 09, 2020.

The relevance of this international conference is confirmed by the fact that the conference was attended by prominent scientists from America, England, Malaysia, Ukraine, India. At an international conference organized by the Financial Institute of India, relevant work was carried out on international cooperation. It was provided and unity was given both on going research in various areas of the economy.

All this should be cross-cutting use of programmatic planning and economics of mathematical purpose.

Most importantly, the prices of the final sale of products should be set proportion to the differentiation of costs and should be monitored fiscal. Here we will carry out the digitalization of the agro-industrial complex.

Among the important projects outlined in the document is the creation of the Digital Agriculture information system. The initiative is undoubtedly of high relevance, and its implementation will significantly increase the efficiency of agriculture.

It should be noted that the first steps in this direction have already been taken. For example, an innovative pilot project for the management of agricultural lands using artificial intelligence is being implemented in the Andijan Technopark. In the course of the project, six areas were selected, which were digitized in vector form and implemented on the Monterra online platform. The owners of agricultural land received recommendations based on the results of research using satellite technology. In addition, at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi, starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, a new direction of the magistracy “Geoinformation systems and technologies” was opened.

The implementation and implementation of the “Digital Agriculture” project will significantly increase the efficiency of land monitoring due to the large coverage of territories, significantly reduce time and financial costs in the field.

Address on January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized that “In agriculture, measures are being taken to increase the interest of farmers and dehkans, the introduction of advanced technologies and the transition to a

cluster production system”

Pursuance of this Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, by order of academician BA Suleimanov, rector of the Tashkent State Agrarian University, under the department of professor M.Kh.Saidov – “Agrologistics”, a school “Digital economy of agroindustry” was opened under the leadership of academician S.S.

At the school, with their scientific knowledge and experience, they conducted classes with young people as the teaching staff of the Tashkent Agrarian University, and also such prominent scientists as B.A. Suleimanov, S.S. Gulfamov, K.A. Abdurakhmonov, U.P. Umurzokov are involved. , A.A. Abduvosikov, M.Kh. Saidov, S. Ismailov, K. Sulstonov and many others.

On October 5, 2020, the President signed a decree “On Approval of the Concept of the National Strategy Digital Uzbekistan 2030”, which contains studies according to which over 67 percent (22.5 million users) of the population of Uzbekistan have access to the Internet. At the same time, the number of third and fourth generation mobile users has exceeded 16 million subscribers.

The economies of developed countries have already entered the era of innovative digitalization. The share of the digital economy in GDP in Uzbekistan is 2.2%. At the same time, the average optimal indicator is considered to be 7-8%, for example, in the UK it is 12.4%, South Korea - 8%, China - 6.9%, India - 5.6%, at the same time in Russia - 2, 8%, Kazakhstan - 3.9%.

On April 28, 2020, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev “On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and electronic government” was adopted. Currently, on the basis of this decree, the widespread introduction of digital technologies is carried out in all sectors of the economy and spheres of public life.

In accordance with the draft Concept for the Development of the Electronic Government System of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is planned to increase the share of ICT services in GDP to 5.0% by 2025, and to 10% by 2030.

Comprehensive measures are being implemented in the republic to actively develop the digital economy, as well as to widely introduce modern information and communication technologies in all sectors and spheres, first of all, in public administration, education, health care and agriculture.

Among the most relevant is the agricultural sector, where serious tasks have been set in terms of the digitalization of the industry.

How serious and important attention is paid to this area is evidenced by the fact that, according to the President’s decree of April 28, “On measures for the widespread

introduction of the digital economy and electronic government,” the post of Deputy Minister for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications, responsible for accelerated digitalization of the agricultural sector, the introduction of modern information systems and software products in the agricultural and food security sectors. Through an emphasis on sustainable resource management, Smart Farming contributes to increased productivity and sustainability

In accordance with this, the Department for the Development of Digital Technologies in the Agricultural Sector and the Department for the Development of Geo information Technologies have been created in the structure of the Ministry.

Among the important projects under the decree is the creation of the Digital Agriculture information system. This project is undoubtedly of high relevance, and its implementation will significantly increase the efficiency of agriculture.

The first steps in this direction have already begun. So, in the Andijan Technopark, an innovative pilot project is being implemented to manage agricultural land using artificial intelligence, increase the yield of agricultural land by introducing modern information and communication technologies, organizing a system to reduce the cost of production and increase the export potential of agricultural enterprises. The process of shaping new digital realities in India was facilitated not only by the efforts of the government, the active actions of Indian business, but also by the joint steps of Indian government agencies and private entrepreneurs, who equally understand the importance, complexity and prospects of digital transformation for the Indian economy and society as a whole.

In 2015, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced the launch of the Digital India campaign, which included a number of important government initiatives related to increasing the digital literacy of the population, developing infrastructure, and creating e-government. Among the most significant successes achieved along this path the completion and implementation of the state system of digital identification of citizens ‘Adhar’, a unified digital tax system, extended to all states that previously had individual tax rules, as well as the development and implementation of the Reserve Bank of India jointly with the Association of Indian Banks of a fast payment system similar to the one created by the Central Bank of Russia.

As the head of the School of Digital Economy of Agroindustry and the Director of the Uzbekistan-Israel Friendship Society, joint work with Israeli companies in the field of drip irrigation is being established, as the whole world knows Israel in this regard has very extensive experience and the task of the School of Digital Economy of Agroindustry is to establish research work involving young professionals and scientists in the industry.

The digital economy is designed not only to increase economic productivity in developing countries, but also to provide people with opportunities for positive change. Just think, digitalization is actually bringing the world together, providing people with the information they need and useful technology.

According to the available data, approximately four billion people on the planet do not have access to the World Wide Web, which is more than half of the world's population. This means that the governments of their countries must by all means work on the implementation of a digital economy that can improve the standard of living of people, providing them with the basic amenities that have become familiar to residents of developed countries. Artificial intelligence, virtual reality, machine learning and other latest technologies are already actively penetrating all areas of industrial life. With each passing day, the boundaries between digital and real economies are blurring and will eventually disappear altogether.

In accordance with the Decrees and Resolutions of the President from 2020, in order to expand market mechanisms in the agricultural sector, to increase the interest of farmers, the state is canceling the market order for cotton and grain.

Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2030 in 2020” dated January 28, 2020 was signed.

The main goal of this concept is to increase the productivity of agricultural crops, increase the productivity of animal husbandry, protect crops and land from pests and various insects, to eliminate the influence of external unfavorable factors on the productivity of various crops, as well as the introduction of modern agricultural methods and an increase in production culture. Particular attention is paid to the introduction of high technologies and digital management in the agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Thanks to the implementation of the Concept, labor productivity in the field will increase by 30 percent, and the cotton harvest will be harvested with full equipment. The creation of stress-resistant, high-yielding, transportable, rich in biological activity varieties of agricultural crops is 100 percent guaranteed. The use of satellite data and remote sensing technologies will make it possible to quickly and accurately assess the condition of agricultural lands and crops grown on them. This will help identify all types of crops in the country and estimate the area.

Another important area is that the number of facilities designed using the “smart greenhouse” technology will be increased to 500. An automated production system will be introduced in animal husbandry, as a result of which the cost of production will decrease by 15 percent.

The transition to digital agriculture in Uzbekistan is being carried out in

collaboration with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Bank. And within the framework of the Concept approved by the Decree of the Head of State of June 17, 2019, a prototype of a special online platform was created for monitoring land used in agriculture through a geographic information system.

Currently, work is underway on the draft State Program “Smart Agriculture”. Improved farming systems install “smart technologies” based on crop and environmental conditions. These include pest and disease detection, climate control, temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide, nutrient supply and irrigation equipment. Using all this guarantees an increase in productivity by at least 30 percent. In addition, improved systems will be introduced into all agricultural production and marketing chains. Eventually, it will be possible to collect large amounts of electronic data. And as a result of their conservation and analysis, it is possible to ensure the efficient use of water, land and other limited resources, the quality and safety of food.

The convenience of the electronic system lies in the fact that even after harvesting it is applicable in the process of processing, packaging, cleaning, sorting, and delivering products. In short, smart farming technologies play an important role in achieving high productivity and quality, reducing water consumption and production costs, planning and forecasting crops. Within the framework of the Presidential Decree of October 5, 2020, the implementation of the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy, a wide range of events is planned. During the digital transformation of regions and industries in 2020-2022.

In recent years, the agricultural sector in our country has transformed from a one-sided development into a multi-profile one. Appropriate measures are being taken to increase the export of agricultural products and ensure the financial and economic stability of suppliers. A number of positive results have been achieved as a result of the modernization of all sectors of industry, the rational use of land and water resources, the introduction of modern resource-saving agricultural technologies and the further deepening of modern market relations. As a result of diversification of agriculture, the share of this sector in GDP reached 17% with an average annual growth rate of 6-7%. The agricultural sector of the economy employs more than 3600 people.

The indicators of the sphere give us full confidence that in the future it will only flourish. Given the steps taken by the government, this process will bear fruit very soon.

References:

1. Usmonova V., Esanov H. THE EXISTING INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 31-40.
2. Usmanova V. INCREASING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 131-138.
3. Botirovna U. V., Shahobiddin K. O 'ZBEKISTONDA ISHSIZLIK MUAMMOSI VA UNIHAL QILISH CHORA TADBIRLARI //INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 35. – С. 332-338.
4. Kamolov D., Ropiyeva F. ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS IN ANCIENT CHINA. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 220-225. – 2023.
5. Усмонова В. ХУДУДЛАРДА ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАР САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ //Economics and education. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 6. – С. 70-74.
6. Сирлибеков Х. Ш. ФАКТОРЫ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОГО ТУРИЗМА (СПА-ТУРИЗМА) В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ РОССИИ //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 92-97.
7. Kamolov D., Karimqulova O. ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC ORGANIZATIONS. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 199-202. – 2023.
8. Sirlibekov K. PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 123-131.
9. Sirlibekov K. EVENT TOURISM CENTERS OF SPAIN //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 161-167.
10. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – С. 348-352.
11. Сирлибеков Х. Ш. Факторы и особенности реализации концепции оздоровительного туризма (СПА-туризма) в современной России //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
12. Соловарова М. А. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕТИ ОТЕЛЕЙ MARRIOTT //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
13. Sirlibekov K. PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (3), 123-131. – 2023.
14. Dostonbek K. SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY //Social science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 128-133.
15. Kamolov D., Kilicheva R. CONFUCIAN AND LEGIST DOCTRINE. Science technology&Digital Finance, 1 (4), 187-192. – 2023.